

**QUESTIONNAIRES FOR THE DISSERTATION PROJECT:
“THE INFLUENCE OF POVERTY ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF
SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN: WESTERN RURAL DISTRICT,
SIERRA LEONE AS A CASE STUDY”**

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Abstract:

This article shows comprehensive strata of questionnaires to be administered for the research on the dissertation topic: “The Influence of Poverty on Academic Performance of School Going Children: Western Rural District, Sierra Leone as a Case Study”. It covers three set of questionnaires for school-going student, teachers and parents. The questionnaire for the school-going pupils will be pre-tested and improved for final administration in schools in collecting appropriate data for final analysis and interpretation of the results.

Keywords: questionnaire, poverty, academic performance

1. Introduction

A questionnaire may be regarded as a form of interview on paper, Yogest Kumar Singh, 2006, views a questionnaire as a form that is prepared and distributed in order to secure responses. This questionnaire designed and constructed with main target of securing information about certain conditions or practices. According to Goode and Hatt, as cited Yogest Kumar Singh, 2006, “a questionnaire is a device for securing answers to question by using a form which the respondent fills himself”. Bar, Davis and Johnson also view a questionnaire as “a systematic compilation of questions that are submitted to a sampling of population from which information is desired.” A questionnaire consists of a number of questions printed or typed in a definite order on a form or set of forms. Quite often

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- (5) Do you like the science subject?
- Yes
 - No
- (6) If no, why?
- Teaching method
 - Teacher's attitude
 - Dislike the subject
- (7) Do your parents help you to do your assignment at home?
- Yes
 - No
- (8) What is the attitude of the Science Teacher?
- Punctual
 - Regular
 - Do not care
 - Absent often
 - Very committed
 - Give assignment and correct them
 - Comes late
 - Very wicked
- (9) How many of you in one seat?
- Alone
 - Two
 - Three
 - More than three

B. School Facilities

- (10) Tick (x) to indicate the items available or not available in school.
- Available
 - Not Available
 - Toilet
 - Spacious Class
 - Good Ventilations
 - Staff Room
 - Principal's Office
 - Store
 - Playing Ground
 - Library

- (11) What is the nature of your school structure?
- Built with cement bricks
 - Thatch/Temporal pan body
 - Converted House structure
 - Any other
 - Built with mud-bricks
- (12) Show what is available in your school.
- Principals' Office
 - School Store
 - School Library
 - Toilet
 - Water/Drinking facilities
 - Electricity/internet
 - Playing Field
- (13) Show the recreational facilities in your school.
- Playing ground
 - Equipment for Exercises
 - Football field
 - Volley ball court
 - Basketball court
- (14) Indicate the other business close to your school.
- Market -----
 - Bar/Ghetto/Club -----
 - Museum -----
 - Internet Café -----
 - Petrol Station -----
- (15) Have you ever gone for a field trip?
- Yes
 - No

Objective II: What Are The Home Facilities for Academic Performance?

A. Facilities

- (16) Indicate the educational facilities available at home. Tick either available or not available.
- Available
 - Not Available
 - Table and Chair
 - Study Room/Library

- Television
- Electricity
- Radio
- Text Book
- Blackboard

B. Food

- (17) How many times do you eat at home a day? (Tick)
- Thrice
 - Twice
 - Once
 - At times non
- (18) Do you have lunch for school every day?
- Yes
 - No
- (19) If yes, indicate how much?
- le1000
 - le 2000
 - le 3000
 - le 4000
 - above le 4000

C. Going to School

- (20) How do you go to school? (Tick)
- On foot
 - Private Car
 - Public Transport
 - Motorbike/ Okada
- (21) How far is your house to school? (Tick)
- Just few meters
 - Half a mile
 - About a mile
 - About one to two miles
 - About two to three miles
 - More than four miles

D. Care Taking

- (22) Which person are you living with?
- Two parents

- Guardian
- Only mother
- Only father
- Grandfather
- Grandmother

E. Parent Education

(23) What is the educational standard of your parents/Guardian? (Tick)

- University
- Secondary School
- Primary
- Never went to School

(24) Do you have extra classes at home?

- Yes
- No

(25) If yes, who teaches you? (Tick)

- Parents/Guardian
- Contracted Teacher
- Friends
- Other relatives

F. Source of Light

(26) What is the source of light for your studies during the night? (Tick)

- Battery light
- Shade lamp
- Candle
- Pan lamp
- Solar light
- Electricity

(27). Do you study every night?

- Yes
- No

(28) If No! Why? (Tick)

- No light
- No space
- No time

G. House Work

- (29) What other chores do you do?
- Sell
 - Farm work
 - Laundering
 - Others
- (30) How many hours do you do these chores for the day? (Tick)
- One hour
 - Two to three hours
 - Four to five hours
 - More than five hours
- (31) What is the effect of your house chores to your school work? (Tick)
- No effect
 - Always weak to study
 - Absent from school
 - Lateness to school

H. Peer Group Influence

- (32) Do you have friends in the neighbourhood?
- Yes
 - No
- (33) If yes, who are they? (Tick)
- Other School pupils
 - Sellers
 - Neighbouring friends
- (34) How do you share your friendship together? (Tick)
- Study together
 - Going to clubs/parties at night
 - Drinking and smoking
 - Watching movies
 - Others
- (35) What is the status of the house you are living? (Tick)
- Parent/Guardian built
 - Rented
 - Family house
 - Office quarter
 - Camp

(36) What is the position of the house? (Tick)

- Flat land
- Hilly site
- Slump area

(37) How is the environment of the house?

- Conducive
- Congestion
- Crowded
- Isolated

I. Health Facilities

(38) Any health facilities around your house?

- Yes
- No

(39) If yes, do you go for treatment when sick? (Tick)

- Always
- At times
- Not at all

(40) If No, why are you not going for treatment? (Tick)

- Parent cannot afford
- Use traditional ways
- Not like

J. School Fees/Uniform

(41) Do you have new school uniform this year?

- Yes
- No

(42) If yes, how did you get it? (Tick)

- Parents made it
- Supply by Government
- Other family members
- Myself

(43) If No, why? (Tick)

- Caretaker cannot afford now
- Death of parent/Guardian
- Due to big family to parent

(44) Do your parents/Guardians pay your school fees on time?

- Yes
- No

(45) If No, why? (Tick)

- Sick
- Bankrupt
- Too much burden
- Not interested in Education
- Refused to pay
- Cannot afford it

(46) Do your parents or Guardians attend CTA meeting?

- Always
- At times
- Not at all

Objective III: What Are the Environmental Conditions That Influence Academic Performance of Students?

(47) Show the environment that you live. Indicate what is available within your environment:

- Market
- Bar/Ghetto
- Museum
- Night Club
- Petrol Station
- Internet Café
- Wharf
- Video centers
- Clinic

(48) Do you like the environment of your school/house?

- Yes
- No

(49) If No, why? (Tick)

- Tight
- Slummy Area
- Crowded
- Smelling

- (50) Do you have a mobile phone?
- Yes
 - No
- (51) If yes, what programs do you like to operate? (Tick)
- WhatsApp
 - Email
 - Facebook
 - IMO
 - WeChat
 - You tube
 - Instagram
 - Others

Objective IV: Measures To Improve Academic Performance

- (52) What was your score in Integrated Science in the past term? (Tick)
- 29 and below
 - 30 to 49
 - 50 and above
- (53) If below 50% why did you fail? (You can tick more than one.)
- I did not study
 - I do not like Integrated Science subject
 - I hate the Integrated Science Teacher
 - I have no time to study at home
 - I do not understand the subject
 - I have never performed an experiment
 - I have never being to a laboratory
- (54) Do you study at home?
- Yes
 - No
- (55) If yes, who helps you? (Tick)
- Parents
 - Friend
 - Assistant Teacher
 - Nobody

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- (56) Can your parents/Guardians read or write?
- Yes
 - No
- (57) What are your hobbies?
- Reading
 - Playing
 - Watching Films
 - Selling
 - others
- (58) What is your parent/guardian daily work? (Write)
-
- (59) What disturbs your academic work? (Tick)
- Selling
 - Playing with Friends
 - Going out to Clubs
 - Hunger
 - Too much work
 - Any other (write if any)
- (60) How many times do you eat a day? (Tick)
- Three or more times
 - Two times
 - Once
 - Nothing at times
- (61) Do you have lunch for school?
- Yes
 - No
- (62) If yes, how much money is given to you a day? (Tick)
- Le1000
 - Le2000
 - Le3000 or Le4000
 - Le5000 and above
- (63) If No, how do you survive in school? (Tick)
- Beg from friends/teacher
 - Go without food in school
 - Work in school for lunch

(64) If no lunch, what is your behaviour in school? (Tick)

- Dull in class
- Cannot concentrate in class
- Do not understand the lesson
- Sleep a lot in class
- Truancy in school
- Unhappy in school
- Weak for academic work
- Happy in the classes
- Good at practical
- Feel good

(65) What are your wishes of improving your academic performance? (Tick)

- Encouragement at home and school
- Support at school and home
- Adequate food at school and home
- Academic support
- Make available learning materials
- Good uniform and dress
- Good teaching methods
- Health facilities in school and home.

2. Questionnaire for Teachers

A. Background Information

1. School:
2. Status:
3. Sex: Age:
4. Religion: Tribe:
5. Region/District:
6. Teaching Experience:
7. Educational Level (Qualification).....

B. Objective 1: What Is the Socio-Economic Factors that Affect/Impact the Performance of a Teacher in School?

- (1) Which school do you teach?
 - Public
 - Private
 - Both

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- (2) Are you on pay roll?
- Yes
 - No
- (3) If no, how do you earn your living?
- (4) If yes, are you paid promptly?
- Yes
 - No
- (5) How long have you taught without salary?
- Less than one year
 - Only one year
 - More than one year
- (6) Do you enjoy credit facilities in your school?
- Yes
 - No
- (7) Do you enjoy micro-credit facilities from banks through your school approval?
- Yes
 - No
- (8) Do you have any other source(s) of income?
- Yes
 - No
- (9) What type of school do you teach?
- Mixed school
 - Boys school
 - Girls school
- (10) Which house do you live?
- Owned house
 - Rented
 - Family
- (11) Do you have access to electricity at home?
- Yes daily
 - Yes but irregular
 - Not at all

(12) Do you have access to water supply at home?

- Yes daily
- Yes but weekly
- Not at all

(13) What is the size of your family?

- Nuclear
- Extended

(14) What available source do you have at home to prepare your lesson note?

- Textbooks
- Old notes
- Internet
- Others

Objective 2: What Are the Facilities Available in School for Academic Performance of School Going Children?

(15) Are you a trained and qualified teacher in Integrated Science?

- Yes
- No

(16) What are your major and minor subjects?

Major

Minor

(17) How long have you been teaching Integrated Science at JSS III?

.....

(18) What is the average class age?

.....

(19) Do you have enough textbooks for the subject?

- Yes
- No

(20) Do you buy textbooks for yourself or the school provides?

- Self-effort
- School
- Government supply

(20) Do you have a school library?

- Yes
- No

(21) If yes, are there enough Integrated Science textbooks available for the children to read?

- Yes
- No

(22) Is the class crowded during integrated science class?

- Yes
- No

(23) Do you have a laboratory for practical?

- Yes
- No

(24) If yes, how many times do you perform experiments per week?

.....

(25) Are there enough materials for practical?

- Yes
- No

(26) Do you have enough BECE past papers in Integrated Science?

- Yes
- No

(27) Do you have a special office as an Integrated Science Teacher?

- Yes
- No

Objective 3: What Are the Measures Taken to Improve Academic Performance of School Going Children?

(28) Are you a teacher on paying roll?

- Yes
- No

(29) Do you have a pin code as a teacher?

- Yes
- No

- (30) Are you a trained and qualified teacher?
- Yes
 - No
- (31) What is your present highest qualification? (Tick)
- TC
 - BSc
 - HTC
 - MA
 - BA
 - MSc
 - No certificate
- (32) Where did you study (College name only)?
..... Year.....
- (33) Do you have problems teaching Integrated Science at JSS III level?
- Yes
 - No
- (34) If yes, what are they?
.....
.....
.....
.....
- (35) If yes, what are your strategies to improve in your teaching?
.....
.....
.....
.....

Objective 4: What Are the Environmental Conditions that Influence Academic Performance of School Going Children?

- (36) How do you view the environment for learning?
- Good
 - Not good
- (37) Do you have a free space for extra curriculum activities?
- Yes
 - No

(38) Do you have space for effective practical?
 Yes
 No

(39) Is your school fenced?
 Yes
 No

(40) Tick the other business available around the school.
 Market
 Bar/Ghetto
 Stadium
 Petrol Station
 Wharf
 Museum
 Night Club
 Cinema Hall
 Others

(41) What are your recommendations for improving academic performance in Integrated Science for JSS III pupils?
i.
ii.
iii.
iv.
v.

Declaration of Consent

I willingly agree to fill this questionnaire in order to contribute meaningfully to the improvement of quality Education in Sierra Leone.

Sign.....

Date.....

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3. Questionnaire for Parents

A. Background Information

Address:

Sex: Age:

Religion: Tribe:

Region/ District:

Occupation:

Sex: Male / Female

(1) What is your Career?

.....

(2) What is your education standard? (Tick)

- Never went to school
- Primary level
- Secondary level
- College level
- University level

(3) What is your relationship with the child?

- Parent
- Relative

(4) Do you live in your own house?

- Yes
- No

(5) If yes, what type of house? (Tick)

- Thatch
- Pan Body
- Cement
- Mud Built

(6) What is the source of power in your house?

- Electricity
- Pan Lamp
- Battery Light
- Solar Bulb
- Shade Lamp

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- (7) If you do not live in your house, where do you live? (Tick)
- Rent
 - Family House
 - Office Quarter
 - Friends
 - Camp
- (8) What type of family do you live with?
- Nuclear
 - Extended
- (9) How many wife/wives do you have? (Only for husbands).
.....
- (10) Are you a single parent? Father/Mother?
- Yes
 - No
- (11) How many children do you have?
.....
- (12) If you have children, are they all going to school?
- Yes
 - No
- (13) Do you responsible for your children's education?
- Yes
 - No
- (14) If yes, does your child eat before going to school?
- Yes
 - No
- (15) Do you give your child lunch for school?
- Yes
 - No
- (16) If yes, how much amount of lunch do you give your child a day?
.....

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(17) How does your child go to school?(Tick)

- Walking
- Public Transportation
- Private Car
- Motorbike
- School bus
- Bicycle

(18) What is the distance from your house to school?

.....

(19) How do you help your child study at home? (Tick)

- Teaching him myself
- Employ a private teacher
- No time for that
- Study with friends
- Study alone

(20) Do you pay your child's fee on time?

- Yes
- No

(21) How many meals can you provide a day for your child at home?

- One
- Two
- Three
- At times nothing

(22) What extra work is your child doing when not going to school?

.....
.....
.....

(23) Do you have any of the following in your house? (Please tick)

- Yes
- No
 - Television
 - Radio
 - Electric Iron
 - Satellite plasma
 - General parlour
 - Dining room

- Individual Rooms
- Study Room
- Bicycles
- Washing Machine
- Fan

(24) Do you attend CTA meetings?

- Yes
- No

(25) Have you ever checked in school to know your child's performance?

- Yes
- No

(26) Does your child improve in Integrated Science?

- Yes
- No

(27) What are your recommendations for your child's improvement in education?

- i.
- ii.
- iii.
- iv.
- v.

Declaration of Consent

I willingly agree to fill this questionnaire in order to contribute meaningfully to the improvement of quality Education in Sierra Leone.

Sign:

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Conclusion

Questionnaire which is an interview in paper, seeks the views of respondents that will help the researcher to know the truth, so that, effective measures would be taken to combat problems under investigation. These questionnaires are meant to have direct communication of feelings, emotions, and behaviors of teachers, parents and school - going children for thorough analysis of the result that will yield fruitful outcome of the research work.

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